

Bicyclo-1,3,3-nonan-2,9-dione (10): It was obtained by the previous general method from 2-(2-methoxy-carbonyl)ethyl)cyclohexanone, (65%), m.p. 141° (Found: C, 71.31; H, 8.46. C₉H₂O₂ calcd. for: C, 72.05; 3.55%; $\lambda_{\max}$ 254 nm (log ϵ 3.72).

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Aflatoxin Analogues as Possible Anti-coagulants. Part-II

G. V. P. CHANDRA MOULI*, R. B. REDDY

and

Y. D. REDDY

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Warangal-506 004

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THE striking characteristic feature of all the aflatoxins which are a group of highly oxygenated and unsaturated compounds, is the presence of di(or tetra)hydro[2,3-*b*]benzofuran¹ structural unit fused to 2-oxopyran unit², which had not been previously noticed in the field of natural products. Some years ago, we reported³ the synthesis of some analogues of aflatoxins containing 4-hydroxycoumarin moiety. We present here the synthesis and anticoagulant activity of some new analogues of aflatoxins.

The active intermediate synthesised (Scheme 1) was 6*a*,9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*]benzopyran-3,8-(7*H*)-dione (3). The synthetic strategy envisaged for construction of 3 was to start from 2,3,3*a*,8*a*-tetrahydro-2-oxo-4-benzyloxy-6-methoxy-furo[2,3-*b*]benzofuran (1),

whose synthesis was reported earlier⁴. It was subjected to demethylation, by its treatment with dry pyridine hydrochloride⁵ in order to convert into the corresponding hydroxy compound (2). For the construction of 4-hydroxycoumarin unit upon 2, the feasibility of two different general routes was considered. In one of the routes, the hydroxy was converted into the malonic ester and later was cyclised⁶ by AlCl₃. In the other method, the hydroxy was directly cyclised⁷ into the required heterocycle by using POCl₃ and ZnCl₂. The second method was found to be more suitable and was made use of in the present investigation for obtaining 3. It also became possible to convert 3 into different dicoumarol derivatives (4*a*–*d*). Thus when formaldehyde, aromatic aldehydes and heteroaryl aldehydes were allowed to react with 3, a number of 2,2'-[substituted-methylene]-bis-[6*b*, 9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*](1)benzopyran-3,8(7*H*)-diones] (4*a*–*d*), were produced.

The investigations upon structure-pharmacological activity relations of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives revealed that electrophilic substituents like aminomethyl and α -acetylbenzyl groups in position-3, increase the anticoagulant activity⁹. A logical extension of this work would be the Mannich reactions of difuro-4-hydroxycoumarin (3) with formaldehyde and various amines¹⁰. Thus 2-(diphenylaminomethyl)-6*b*,9*a*-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3*H*-furo(3',2' : 4,5)-furo[2,3-*f*](1)benzopyran-3,8(7*H*)-dione (5) was prepared. Similarly, a warfarin analogue of aflatoxins 6 was also synthesised by Micheal addition of an α,β -unsaturated ketone namely benzalacetone¹¹ upon 3. Also a coumarinochromone derivative (7) of the reactive intermediate (3) was obtained by a reaction between 3 and *o*-bromobenzoic acid in the presence of cupric chloride and organic base like pyridine¹².

All the structures have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, uv, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. These compounds exhibit general uv absorption bands at 225, 275 and 310 nm (cinnamoyl chromophore) which are similar to the spectra of aflatoxins¹³. These bands are slightly shifted in basic medium and located around 217, 242(s), 275(s), 280(m) and 302(s)¹⁴. The ir spectra include absorptions around 1785, 1760 and 1688 cm⁻¹, indicating the *cis*-fusion of the five-membered ring system¹⁵. The peak at 1785 cm⁻¹ in all these compounds is due to a ν -lactone anticipated to be exceptionally good hydrogen bond acceptor¹⁶. The enolic hydroxyl is located around 3050 cm⁻¹. The ¹H nmr spectra of 3 reveal signals for H_a and H_b at δ 2.9–3.2 (2H, d), H_c around δ 5.6–6.0 (1H, d) and H_d around δ 3.8 (1H, m). The signal at δ 3.2 is due to benzylmethylene. The aromatic proton of the main skeleton is located at δ 6.4–6.5 (1H, m) and the side-chain aromatic protons are around δ 7.2–7.5 (5H, m, benzyloxy). The vinyl proton at position-3 is identified at δ 5.4 (1H, s) and the enolic proton at δ 12.2. There are some minute deviations in chemical shifts from the values identified by

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANTICOAGULANT ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	Physical data		Mol. formula	Anticoagulant activity	
		M.p. °C			Increase in prothrombin time over normal (s)	Relative anticoagulant index
1	60	166-7		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₅	Nil	Nil
2	62	272-3		C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅	Nil	Nil
3	38	267		C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₇	24.26	16.81
4a	29	258-9		C ₄₁ H ₃₇ O ₁₄	64.2	57.07
4b	32	311-2		C ₄₉ H ₄₁ O ₁₄ N	44.16	20.13
4c	35	241-2		C ₅₁ H ₃₄ O ₁₄	92.8	41.2
4d	25	302-3		C ₅₀ H ₃₂ O ₁₆	58.2	39.8
5	28	298-9		C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ N	3.03	2.51
6	42	287-8		C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₉	36.5	29.12
7	31	227		C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇	Nil	Nil

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

Knight¹⁷. The ¹H nmr signals for the basic skeleton in almost all the compounds are the same. However deviations are observed for compound 4a, where the vinylic proton is totally absent and the integration for the remaining protons is double indicating the formation of bis-product. The exocyclic methylene protons for 4a at the ring junction¹⁸ are located around δ 2.2-2.3 (2H, s) which also offer ample support for the formation of the bis-product. Satisfactory chemical shifts are observed for the remaining.

Anticoagulant activity: The compounds were screened for anticoagulant activity upon albino (*Mus ratus*) by the method of Quick *et al.*¹⁹. The average increase in prothrombin time of plasma (12.5%) over the normal was noted in the heart puncture method. The relative anticoagulant index was calculated for each compound. The index serves as an approximate basis for the comparison of the activity. Compounds 1, 2 and 7 did not show any activity, may be due to the absence of enolic hydroxyl function.

Experimental

The uv spectra were recorded in methanolic solution and methanolic sodium hydroxide solution using a Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a Varian A-60 instrument, chemical shifts downfield from TMS as internal standard. Tlc was used for monitoring reactions and separations. Plates coated with Mark silica gel G was developed with 3–5% methanol in chloroform. Melting points were uncorrected.

2,3,3a,8a-Tetrahydro-2-oxo-4-benzyloxy-6-hydroxy-furo[2,3-b]benzofuran (2): Dry pyridine hydrochloride (6.96 g) was added to 2,3,3a,8a-tetrahydro-2-oxo-4-benzyloxy-6-methoxy-furo[2,3-b]benzofuran (**1**; 2.1 g) and the reaction mixture was heated for 30 min at 220–25°. Water was then added to the cooled reaction mixture and the crude product extracted with 4% sodium hydroxide. Acidification of the above solution gave the title compound as brown powder (1.6 g) after recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether.

6b,9a-Dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3H-furo(3',2':4,5)-furo[2,3-f]benzofuran-3,8(7H)-dione (3): The benzyloxyhydroxydifuro intermediate (**2**; 2.8 g) was mixed with malonic acid (1.1 g), phosphorous oxychloride (2.8 g) and anhydrous zinc chloride (4.2 g). The mixture was heated at 60–5° for 36 h with continuous stirring, then cooled, decomposed, filtered, and the solid washed and recrystallised from benzene as pale yellow crystals.

2,2'-(Substituted-methylene)-bis-(6b,9a-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3H-furo(3',2':4,5)-furo[2,3-f](1)benzopyran-3,8(7H)-dione (4a-d). General procedure: To a stirred suspension of **3** (0.02 mol) in aqueous ethanol, an alcoholic solution of the required aldehyde (0.01 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h. The solid separated was filtered, washed, dried, separated by tlc and crystallised from dioxan-chloroform mixture.

2-(Diphenylaminomethyl)-6b,9a-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3H-furo(3',2':4,5)furo[2,3-f](1)benzopyran-3,8(7H)-dione (5): Diphenylamine (0.14 g) in absolute ethanol (3 ml) was treated with formaldehyde (0.12 g; 40%), followed by the addition of benzyloxydifuro-4-hydroxycoumarin (**3**; 0.49 g) in absolute ethanol (8 ml) at the boiling point of the ethanolic solution. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and allowed to stand at 5° overnight. The resulting solid was washed with dry ether, purified by ptc on silica gel and recrystallised from chlorobenzene as yellow needles.

2-[1-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)-3-oxo-butyl]-6b,9a-dihydro-1-hydroxy-6-benzyloxy-3H-furo(3',2':4,5)-furo[2,3-f](1)benzopyran-3,8(7H)-dione (6): *p*-Methoxybenzalacetone (1.05 g) was added to a solution of compound **3** (0.05 g) in dioxan (10 ml) containing a drop of piperidine. The mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h and the resulting solid was washed with

toluene, resolved on ptc and recrystallised from benzene as colourless plates.

3a,14a-Dihydro-4-benzyloxy-7H,8H-(1)benzopyrano[3,2-c]furo(3',2':4,5)furo[2,3-f](1)benzopyran-2,7,8(3H)-trione (7): A mixture of **3** (0.37 g), *o*-bromobenzoic acid (1.3 g), dry pyridine (35 ml) and anhydrous cupric chloride (1.5 g) was refluxed for 6 h. Pyridine was then removed by distillation and the residue poured into ice-cold HCl (200 ml; 1:1). The light yellow crystalline product that separated was recrystallised from benzene (0.17 g).

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